

Complaint Procedure System

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Abstract

Online Complaint Procedure System provides an online way of solving the problems faced by the public by saving time and eradicate corruption.

The objective of the complaints management system is to make complaints easier to coordinate, monitor, track and resolve, and to provide company with an effective tool to identify and target problem areas, monitor complaints handling performance and make business improvements. Online Complaint Procedure is a management technique for assessing, analyzing and responding to customer complaints. Complaints management software is used to record resolve and respond to customer complaints, requests as well as facilitate any other feedback.

Keywords: online, complaint, management, respond, customer.

Introduction

The main objective of this Complaint Management system is to focus on the issues related to internal system. Complaint Management system is a platform independent application, so this web application can be accessed anywhere in the system. This is also developed for reduces the communication cost between the staffs and to provide the efficient service to their staffs.

The system need to provide the services to the user who is accessing this system from the collected information and this system gathering Call Registration about the issues to provide services. This system which could enhance the day to day activities of the business with efficiency and correctness. Once the call Registered by the staff/user, it should be assigned to service engineers and update the calls as quickly as possible. There are various modules involved in the system.

Objective

The objective of the complaints management system is

1. To make complaints easier to coordinate, monitor, track and resolve,
2. To provide company with an effective tool to identify and target problem areas, monitor complaints handling performance
3. To make business improvements.
4. Prompt and specific retrieval of data.
5. Flexibility in the system according to the changing environment.
6. Controlling redundancy in storing the same data multiple times.
7. Accuracy, timeliness and comprehensiveness of the system output.
8. Stability and operability by people of average intelligence.
9. Enhancement in the completion of work within the constraints of time.

Scope

This policy is designed to provide a mechanism by which a customer may lodge a

complaint regarding a service or electronic way. Through this process the online and mobile gadgets seeks to ensure the provision of a quality and excellent support services for customer. Further, the process is intended to identify opportunities to improve service and customer satisfaction, as well as demonstrate compliance with federal regulations regarding the receipt, response to and tracking of customer complaints.

Literature Review

A complaint has been defined as an action taken by an individual, which involves communicating something negative regarding a product or service, to either the firm manufacturing or marketing the product or service, or to some third party entity (Jacoby and Jaccard 1981). Resnik and Harmon (1983) treat it as 'overt manifestation of dissatisfaction'. Singh and Howell (1985), as quoted by Shamdasani (1988), define consumer-complaining behavior to include "all non-behavioral and behavioral responses, which involve communicating something negative, regarding a purchase episode and is triggered by perceived dissatisfaction(s) with that episode." The present study adopts the definitions cited hereunder, as the meaning of complaint handling/ complaint redressal and complaint respectively: Complaint handling can be viewed as a sequence of events in which a procedure, beginning with communicating the complaint, generates a process of interaction through which a decision and outcome occurs (Tax, Brown and Chandrashekar 1998).

3.1 MODULES DESCRIPTION

3.1.1 CALL REGISTRATION MODULE

User's/Staff fully deals with call registration details. User can able to register the call based on Issue category and Issue sub category, also give his location, email, phone Number and saved the details. Issue Status is always open in this module.

3.1.2 CALL UPDATE MODULE

In this Module Service Engineer can able to see his assigned calls and track the issues and update the call as closed otherwise admin can change the service engineer in this call. Status changed to closed

3.1.3 LISTING MODULE

This module lists all the call registration details, it contains call status and date of registration and if it is assigned to service engineer then engineer name displayed and edit the call registration and also update the status.

Detailed Life Cycle of the project

This document is created for documenting all major classes which are used in project. The relationship between the classes and how the classes are interacting (Process flow / DFD diagram) are documented in low level design document.

Data Flow Diagram- A graphical tool used to describe and analyses the moment of data through a system manual or automated including the process, stores of data, and delays in the system. DFD is the basis from which other components are developed. The transformation of data from input to output, through processes, may be described logically and independently of the physical components associated with the system.

Second Level Data Flow Diagram

3.0 Search Process

4.0 Login Process

9.1.2. CALL REGISTRATION PAGE:

Data structure

Database name: job

1. Table name: admin

Description: To store the admin username and password.

Primary Key: id

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
1	id	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT
2	username	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
3	password	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
4	updateDate	varchar(255)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	

2. Table name: user

Description: To store the add data.

Primary Key: Id

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes
1	id	int(11)		
2	fullName	varchar(255)	latin1_swedish_ci	
3	userEmail	varchar(255)	latin1_swedish_ci	
4	password	varchar(255)	latin1_swedish_ci	
5	contactNo	bigint(11)		
6	address	tinytext	latin1_swedish_ci	

2. Methodology

PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) is a widely-used open source server-side scripting language for web development and can be embedded into HTML. PHP pages contain HTML with embedded code [23]. PHP offers several advantages:

- PHP runs on different platforms (Windows, Linux, Unix, etc.).
- PHP is compatible with almost all servers used today (Apache, IIS, etc.).
- PHP is free to download from the official PHP resource: www.php.net.

2.1 JavaScript

JavaScript is a client side scripting language designed to add interactivity to HTML pages. A scripting language is a lightweight programming language. It is usually embedded directly into HTML pages. It is an interpreted language which allows the scripts to execute without preliminary compilation. JavaScript can react to events. A JavaScript can be set to execute when something happens, like when a page has finished loading or when a user clicks on an HTML element. JavaScript can read and write HTML elements and can also change its content and properties. A JavaScript can be used to validate form data before it is submitted to a server. This saves the server from extra processing. A JavaScript can be used to detect the visitor's browser, and depending on the browser, load another page specifically designed for that browser.

2.2 MYSQL

MySQL is a database server is ideal for both small and large applications. It supports standard SQL and compiles on a number of platforms.

2.3 HTML

HTML stands for Hyper Text Markup Language. A markup language is a language that annotates text in a way that is syntactically distinguishable so that the computer can manipulate it. It is a set of markup tags used to describe web pages. The tags are what separate normal text from HTML code. They are the words between the <angle-brackets>. Different tags will perform different functions, like rendering images or tables. It is a combination of words and symbols which give instructions on how the document will be presented. The tags themselves don't appear when you view your page through a browser, but their effects do.

2.4 CSS

CSS stands for Cascading Style Sheets. It is used to control the style and layout of multiple web pages all at once. Styles define

how to display HTML elements. CSS overrides the browser's default settings for interpreting how tags should be displayed, letting you use any HTML element indicated by an opening and closing tag to apply style attributes defined either locally or in a style sheet. External Style Sheets can save a lot of work. They are stored in CSS files.

2.5 Feasibility Study

An analysis and evaluation of a proposed project to determine if it

1. Is technically feasible.
2. Is feasible within the estimated cost.
3. Will be profitable.

Feasibility studies are almost always conducted where large sums are at stake.

2.6 Coding

The basic role of this phase is to convert designing into code using the programming language decided in designing phase.

An introductory example,

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Example</title>
</head>
<body>
<?php echo "Hi, I'm a PHP script!"; ?>
</body>
</html>
```

Conclusions

The system has the benefits of easy access because it is be developed as a platform independent web application, so the admin can maintain a proper contact with their users, which may be access anywhere . All communications between the client/user and administrator has done through the online, so this communication cost also be reduced

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